

Spectrophotometric determination of nickel using sulfosalicylic acid

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A simple and rapid spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel has been developed using sulfosalicylic acid. The pink coloured 1 : 1 complex formed shows the absorption maximum at 510 nm. The method is free from interference from many of the associated metal ions. It obeys the Beer's law in the range 2–20 ppm of Ni^{II} with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $6.69 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.083 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Analysis of various alloys has been carried out satisfactorily.

The earlier reagents used for spectrophotometric determination of nickel are dimethyl glyoxime^{1,2} in chloroform and ammoniacal medium. In chloroform medium Fe^{III}, Cr^{III} and Cu^{II} cause interference. Cycloheptanedionedioxime has been used for the extraction of nickel³, but the method is time-consuming having low sensitivity. Traces of nickel is also determined by converting into a complex of nickel-dimethylthiocarbamate⁴. This method is sensitive but not selective since Cu, Bi and Co interfere. Some other reagents have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel include, 3-hydroxy-3-*n*-propyl-1-*p*-carboxyphenyl-triazole⁵, hydrazine hydrate⁶, sodium isoamyl xanthate in the presence of surfactants⁷.

In the present investigation, sulfosalicylic acid has been used as a selective, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of nickel.

Results and discussion

Sulfosalicylic acid forms a soluble 1 : 1 complex with nickel(II). The pink coloured complex has an absorption maximum at 510 nm. Nickel(II) reacts with sulfosalicylic acid instantaneously at RT. The colour development is observed only at pH 9–11. The maximum absorbance was found at pH 11. The absorption spectra of sulfosalicylic acid by taking water as blank showed λ_{max} at 314 nm, whereas the nickel-sulfosalicylic acid complex showed λ_{max} at 510 nm against reagent blank.

Beer's law was obeyed up to 20.0 ppm of nickel. The regression coefficient value for the Beer's law straight line is 0.9902. The optimum range for accurate determination was deduced from Ringbom's plot⁸ and found to be 2.0–20.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity⁹ for 20 ppm were found to be $6.69 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.083 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The standard deviation

calculated for six determinations of 8 and 12 ppm were 0.002 and 0.009 respectively. The stability constant of the nickel-sulfosalicylic acid complex calculated by Turner Anderson method¹⁰ was 3.74×10^3 .

The effect of varying amount of the reagent sulfosalicylic acid on the colour development was studied with a solution containing 20 ppm of nickel(II). Maximum of 6 ml of 0.2% aqueous solution of sulfosalicylic acid was needed for the maximum colour development.

The effects of some ions that often accompany nickel(II) were studied by adding different amounts to 8 ppm of nickel(II) solution. An error of $\pm 3\%$ in the absorbance readings was considered tolerable. The tolerance limit (ppm) of various ions were found to be as follows : fluoride, iodide, oxalate, sulfate, citrate (250); acetate, nitrite, perchlorate, borate, phosphate (200); Mo^{VI}, nitrate (150); W^{VI}, bromide, chloride (100); Cr^{III}, Ti^{IV} (75); Cu^{II} (masked by 2-mercaptoethanol), Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} (masked by fluoride) (50); V^{IV} (40); Hg^{II} (masked by chloride), Tl^{III}, U^{VI} (25); Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Al^{III} (10).

Alloy samples and artificial mixtures corresponding to the Ni-Cu-Cr, Ni-Fe, Ni-Mn, Ni-Cu and Ni-Cr alloy composition were prepared and the nickel content was determined by the proposed method and standard deviation was found to be 0.09, 0.09, 0.09, 0.01 and 0.05 ppm respectively (average of six determinations). The interference due to Cu was masked by 2-mercaptoethanol. The results obtained by analysing alloy samples are summarised in Table 1. The nickel content in alloys was also determined by the dimethyl glyoxime method¹¹.

Conclusion : The reagent provides a simple, rapid and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel. The reagent has the advantage of high sensitivity, selectivity, optimum pH range and low absorbance of the

Table 1. Determination of nickel(II) in alloys

Alloy*	Nickel present (%)	Dimethyl glyoxime method		Sulfosalicylic acid method	
		Nickel** found (%)	Standard deviation (%)	Nickel** found (%)	Standard deviation (%)
Permalloy	78.51	78.21	0.15	78.20	0.25
Nomag	11.05	11.08	0.01	11.10	0.02
Nichrome	60.03	59.88	0.11	59.88	0.11
Monel metal	66.98	66.76	0.18	66.76	0.18
Alnico	20.10	20.08	0.01	20.07	0.01
Constantan	39.78	39.74	0.04	39.74	0.04

*All the alloys were supplied by Vittal Das Mohan Lal Ltd., Mumbai, India. **Average of five determinations.

reagent blank. The method needs neither heating for the complete colour development nor extraction into any organic phase. Most of the metal ions, associated with nickel in alloy do not interfere, hence the method can be used for the analysis of alloys and artificial mixtures for their nickel contents.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Standard stock solution (1000 ppm) of nickel (II) was prepared by dissolving nickel ammonium sulfate hexahydrate (Ranbaxy) in water and standardized¹¹ was then suitably diluted to prepare standard solutions. A 0.2% aqueous sulfosalicylic acid (Qualigens) was used. Buffer solutions of suitable pH were prepared by mixing borax, potassium hydrogenphthalate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, KCl, HCl and NaOH in proper proportions. It was then suitably diluted to prepare standard solutions.

A Secomam Anthelie NUA 022 UV-visible spectrophotometer was used with 1 cm quartz cell. A WTW pH330 pH meter was used.

Procedure : Aliquots (0.5–8.0 ml) of the stock solution containing 2–32 ppm of Ni^{II} were pipetted out into a series of 25 ml standard flasks and to each 0.2% aqueous solution of sulfosalicylic acid (8 ml) was added and made up to the mark using buffer solution of pH 11. The solutions were then shaken well and the absorbances was measured at 510 nm against a reagent blank.

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